

Web Appendix 3 - Extended Discussion of Results

A step-by-step description of the evaluation process for an article is available in Web Appendix 1. The scores and detailed evaluations generated by ChatSDG+RR7 served as input to the editorial review process (Table 2). Based on these scores, there were 155 recommendations of acceptance and 13 receiving a rejection recommendation, with 154 suggesting a more thorough review. Then, the normal editorial process proceeded, albeit with ChatSDG+RR7 in tow. The editorial process agreed on the acceptance recommendation for 131 out of the 155 and agreed 100% of the time on the rejections. This is of particular interest since in the previous sample, there was some disagreement on rejections. Also of interest is for those in the neutral recommendation zone, only 66 of the 154 were accepted: a rate of acceptance (43%) well below the overall acceptance rate (61.2%).

Table 2

Overview data of AI-human collaboration in decision making for 322 RRBM Honor Roll submissions

1) AI-Assisted Editor Decisions				
	Pass	Cut	Total	Agreement rate
ChatSDG+RR7: Recommend Pass	131	24	155	84.52%
ChatSDG+RR7: No Recommendation	66	88	154	
ChatSDG+RR7: Recommend Cut	0	13	13	100.00%
	197	125	322	
Combined editor acceptance rate				61.18%

The findings are categorized into two primary types: convergent assessment and divergent assessment. Convergence refers to cases where both the editor and ChatSDG+RR7 agreed on

whether to include or exclude a submission from the Honor Roll, while divergence indicates disagreement between their evaluations. To assess alignment, we used F1 scores, which are performance metrics commonly used in information retrieval and machine learning to evaluate the balance between precision and recall. Precision measures how many of the predicted positives are actually correct, while recall measures how many of the actual positives were correctly predicted. The F1 score is the harmonic mean of the two measures. These scores do not indicate statistical significance or hypothesis testing; rather, they measure the practical accuracy of the AI's decisions in comparison to human judgments. A closer look at this analysis can be found in [Web Appendix 4: F1 Score Analysis](#). Our findings suggest that ChatSDG+RR7 and the editor exhibit a high level of agreement, indicating a low rate of what Bradlow and Wainer (1998) call “rescoring errors.” The results reflect alignment in decision quality, not independent statistical correlation. This high correlation suggests that in most cases, the AI “rescore” aligns well with the editor’s initial judgment minimizing errors and fortifying the agreement in this instantiation of AI-human collaboration. Overall, as a major finding of our study, the 84.52% and 100.00% exceeded a reasonable expectation of an agreement rate appropriate for this research domain (Borgen *et al.*, 2024).

This comparison with historical human decisions allows us to explore both the areas of convergence, where the system aligns with human judgment, and divergence, where discrepancies reveal insights into biases, evolving decision criteria, or potential inconsistencies. The F-score analysis allowed us to fine-tune our thresholds, finding that a single “Pass/Cut” point of score 4.45 optimized for F1 (precision and recall), where a “No Recommendation” range of 4.25 to 4.45 optimized for precision. These findings will help contextualize the implications of

using automated systems alongside human oversight, particularly in shaping the “ground truth” (Kang, E., 2023) for future decision-making.

Specifically, a Type I error occurred when the editor-in-chief disagreed with an AI recommendation of “Pass” or “Cut” (a false positive), and a Type II error occurred whenever the AI recommended “No Recommendation” (a false negative). Both types of errors suggest an underlying and potentially erroneous assumption that the editor-in-chief serves as the superior adjudicator of ground truth. While the editor's unchallengeable position might logically imply the superiority of their judgment, what if their judgment is incorrect?

References

Borgen, H., et al. (2024) 'Private sensitive content on social media: An analysis and automated detection for Norwegian', *Linköping Electronic Conference Proceedings*, 208, pp. 3–10.

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Bradlow, E.T. and Wainer, H. (1998) 'Some statistical and logical considerations when rescaling tests', *Statistica Sinica*, pp. 713–728.

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